

‘I Made it Myself’

DIY in the Design of Assistive Devices for Stroke Patients

Correia de Barros, Ana * Duarte, Carlos ** Cruz, José Bulas ***

* *UTAD – UNIDCOM/IADE*
Lisbon, Portugal, anacorreiadebarros@gmail.com

** *UNIDCOM / IADE*
Lisbon, Portugal, carlos.duarte@iade.pt

*** *UTAD*
Vila Real, Portugal, jacruz@utad.pt

Abstract: As with other people with disabilities, stroke patients could benefit from the use of assistive devices to increase independence and promote their quality of life. However, a phenomenon of rejection and abandonment of assistive devices has been verified. This paper discusses the reasons for this phenomenon, while it introduces the concept of DIY assistive devices which emerged from the findings of spontaneous inventions created by stroke patients and their caregivers. It is argued that a participatory design approach based on DIY could bring benefits to the emotional response of stroke patients towards assistive devices, thus increasing their independence, self-esteem and quality of life.

Key words: *Independent living, participatory design, DIY, inclusive design.*

1. Introduction

As being in the “stone age” [1]. This was how Papanek (1972) evaluated the design stage regarding assistive devices for the elderly and people with disabilities in the 70’s. In a nutshell, assistive devices are those objects which help people with disabilities to compensate or alleviate their impairments in daily tasks. Nowadays, the problem is still being discussed, with authors stating that there is not enough offer on the market to fulfil the users’ needs, whether functionally or emotionally.

Everyday there are 144 new cases of stroke in Portugal [2]. Of these, 30% to 50% survive. More than half of stroke survivors become dependent of others for their daily activities [3], with stroke being in fact the leading cause in Portugal for dependence [2]. Data from the literature suggests that the use of assistive devices increases independence and promotes quality of life to its users [4, 5, 6, 7]. On the other hand, several studies report high rates of assistive device rejection and abandonment. Some of the reasons pointed out as responsible for these phenomena are lack of product functionality, cost and stigma [8, 9, 10]. Furthermore, the low rate of assistive device use has also been associated with lack of information regarding the devices [8].

In trying to increase the usage rate of assistive devices, some authors within healthcare research have proposed frameworks to better understand the users and predict their reactions towards assistive devices [11, 12, 13]. The frameworks are intended to provide better service and more suitable attribution of assistive devices to people with disabilities. Nevertheless, to our knowledge, there is little research on the design itself. That is to say,

several variables such as personality traits, living arrangements and environment or social support are entered into these frameworks, but the design of the assistive devices is not being fully accounted for in healthcare literature.

In design related literature, however, this has been a growing concern. In healthcare literature the importance of including users in the assistive device selection phase is frequently mentioned; in design literature this inclusion of the final users means a participatory design approach, involving users throughout the design process, from idea generation to evaluation of final products. However, this would imply that designers working with users would have good knowledge about the users' disabilities, their concerns, needs and expectations. In other words, beyond being familiar with the physical problems faced by users with disabilities and ergonomics concerning task performance, the designers should also be able to understand the users emotionally. Involving users in the design process with designers trained to understand users both functionally and emotionally (including socially and culturally as well) means the adoption of an empathic design approach [14]. Empathic design research, although mainly consisting in qualitative data collection, has been said to help designers in the development of better solutions for their users because it involves designers resonating with users' problems and immersing into intangible aspects, such as people's 'feelings, emotions, dreams, aspirations and fears' [14].

While at present designers and rehabilitation specialists are doing their work separately, stroke patients are also trying to solve their problems related to assistance in daily living. And they are doing this on their own by creating artisanal solutions on a "Do-it-Yourself" (DIY) basis, making use of the resources at hand and of their own creativity. Throughout the paper we will try to give an account of how these three groups could benefit from working together, by working with the creative potential of stroke victims.

2. The specific case of stroke patients

Although reasons for assistive device abandonment and rejection can be generalized, the issue with emotional responses is that they vary greatly with human diversity. In trying to insert stroke patients within a cluster, it could be said these patients belong to the group of people with acquired disabilities, who have been said to react differently to assistive devices in comparison to other groups such as people who have lived with disabilities from birth [15]. On the other hand, given the particular age incidence of stroke, patients could also fit in the elderly group and in the group of people with growing disabling conditions. The heterogeneity of stroke patients makes the process of predicting their emotional reactions to assistive devices somewhat difficult, especially when considered in this regard of including stroke patients in other generalized groups.

There are, however, a set of recurring characteristics in stroke patients which could point directions as how to design assistive devices for this population. Characteristics such as depression and anxiety should be accounted for, as well as lack of interest, 'emotionalism' (emotional overreactions) [16], sadness and the feeling of uncertainty towards the future, which could explain depressive states in the future if patients' initial expectations are not achieved [17]. On the other hand, Ellis-Hill and Horn (2000) also report that stroke patients still feel as friendly, calm, caring and hopeful as they were prior to the stroke. Common concerns are lack of activity, lack of belongingness feelings, lack of status [18] and an overall feeling of fear regarding assistive devices and task performing [19, 20]. Understanding these concerns is crucial to the *appraisal* framework within theories of emotion [21], and thus to predict users' emotional reactions to assistive devices. Desmet and Hekkert (2007) draw from the theory of Ortony et al. (1988), by dividing concerns into goals, agents and attitudes [22]. Our

research has shown that, for stroke victims, the most important goals have to do with safety, autonomy, social life and activity. Agents have to do with the self, caregivers and professionals providing support in daily life. Attitudes, which have been said to be related to object appeal, have two sides: on the one hand some users are concerned about the stigmatizing characteristics of assistive devices (thus the need for an inclusive design approach), but on the other hand, aesthetics might be in the shadow of what people consider to be primary goals, such as safety, thus losing some of its importance.

So, instead of studying a generalized group such as ‘the disabled’ or ‘the elderly’, we found it more appropriate to study a narrower group at a time (starting with the group of stroke patients) to allow for more assertive guidelines to help predict the emotional response of these specific users towards assistive devices.

3. DIY

In Portugal, as in other countries of the World, assistive devices can be prescribed by medical doctors and be provided at a low or null price to users in need of them. However, due to possible fails in the system, lack of information or lack of suited objects to their needs, users sometimes turn to themselves and their informal caregivers to find the solutions for their daily problems. This results in the development of spontaneous inventions.

The phenomenon of users developing their own products through artisanal approaches is often associated with the presence of 6 conditions: urgent need for a solution to unmet needs, lack of time to require professional services, lack of components in the conventional market, lack of financial resources, lack of adequate ergonomics solutions and poor adaptation to intended environment of use [23]. It is probably worth remembering that, in healthcare literature, some of these conditions have been said to be the cause for patients’ rejection and abandonment of assistive devices [11, 15]. Given these conditions, individuals evaluate their needs, the available resources and come up with an idea to solve the problem. In the Brazilian language there is a word for this type of spontaneous inventions: ‘gambiarra’.

Bouffleur (2006), who has studied the ‘gambiarra’ phenomenon in Brazil advocates for the process of DIY as one which conveys positive emotional outcomes to the ‘gambiarra’ developers. Shove, Watson, Hand and Ingram (2007) have argued the importance of DIY projects regarding the maintenance of self-esteem, allowing self-expression and engagement of the users through knowledge acquisition [24]. Beyond the emotional gains of acquiring knowledge and exercising skills, the DIY process is said to trigger an emotional bond between the user/creator and the created object through the enhancement of the feeling of belongingness and construction of personal identity [25]. And it has also been identified as a process which could give a positive contribution to sustainability [25]. Furthermore, not exactly related to DIY, but to some form of personal adaptation of own objects, the personalization of products has been found to be a possible means to enable self-expression and enhance the attachment one could experience with a given product [26].

Although the term ‘gambiarra’ could be used to define any type of object, there are specific examples of the invention of alternative assistive devices. Looking on the internet, several groups of discussion and sharing of personal inventions can be found. Usually these groups are created for users with similar disabilities, such as stroke, spinal cord injury or arthritis. *Spinalistips* is a Swedish website created by two occupational therapists who realized at some point that the best solutions for everyday problems came from the patients themselves. As a result, they decided to create a website for patients to share their ideas and inspire others with them [27]. The

users in this group upload images of their creations that are intended to show new methods for task performance or DIY instructions to the development of low-cost assistive devices. Other examples are the development of books with tips for people with different types of disabilities to help them cope with everyday challenges, through the sharing of ingenious methods to accomplish several tasks [28]. Nowhere are designers to be found in these approaches, inventions and discussions nowadays.

The result is that, clearly, there are several unmet needs felt by people with disabilities, but little awareness from designers to these needs and artisanal solutions created by the users. A good opportunity for new product development is thus being lost. Design has been said to be in fact a set of capacities and capabilities [29]. Once being [cap]able to recognize and learn with the users' capacities and capabilities, designers could not only benefit from these insights, but also make a great contribution to the delivery of better solutions to these users.

4. Meeting the users

To better understand what were the daily difficulties stroke patients experienced and what types of assistance they used for task accomplishment, semi-structured interviews were carried out with 67 patients in Northern Portugal. The interviews also comprised the application of the Barthel Index (BI) (a scale used in healthcare to evaluate degree of dependence) [30]. Patients were to respond to 42 activities of daily living according to their degree of capability. When assistance was mentioned, patients were asked to describe what type of assistance it was, i.e. personal, equipment or both. Interviews took place at physical therapy clinics and at the patients' houses, allowing in the latter situations for the researchers to photograph the home environments and the assistive devices patients used as well as witness and document how users performed some of their daily activities.

4.1. Spontaneous Inventions

The results have confirmed the data in the literature concerning low use of assistive devices, since the average of assistive device per person is 1.2. There was a high percentage of 'incapable' followed by 'totally capable' answers regarding activities of daily living, denoting two opposite extremes of capability. The BI mean result was 58.1 (SD 29.0), a number close to 60, which is the value considered to be representative of the difference between dependency and minor dependency [31].

When asked whether or not they were aware of the existence of an official list of assistive devices available for prescription (based on the ISO 9999:2007), stroke patients stated they did not know about it, nor were they told by their doctor about the assistive devices they could be offered by social security. Most of the assistive devices used were mobility aids, followed by bathing aids. These seem to be the better known amongst the patients and their caregivers. Maybe the reason for this awareness is because mobility aids are more often seen in the street and bathing aids are present in hospital settings. In comparison to these types of devices, the use of other types of devices, namely daily living aids, such as aids for eating or dressing, were by far much less used. Fifty-three assistive devices were mentioned by the patients as being used in their daily lives. Within those, 21 (39.6%) were uncommon assistive devices. By 'uncommon' we mean all objects which are not officially considered to be assistive devices, since they are not contemplated in the annual homologated list of assistive devices provided by the government. The patients' disposition to use assistive devices in general is correlated to the number of uncommon assistive devices they make use of, which is shown by a positive correlation between number of assistive devices and number of uncommon assistive devices per person, $r = .48$ (one-tailed) $< .01$.

Facing lack of information and economic resources along with the urgency to fulfil basic needs, patients and their caregivers create their own solutions to the problems through ingenious approaches. In some cases patients presented homemade solutions of devices that already existed in the market but of which they were not aware of. One example of this type of situation is the case of a patient with difficulties bending down, whose wife, due to back problems also found it difficult to perform the same movement. One of the problems for this couple was putting shoes on. They went on trying to figure out how they could solve this problem. The wife went to meet a shoemaker and asked him if he could design a device with a long handle and a flat end so that she and his husband could use it to help them put their shoes on. Eventually the shoemaker told the patient's wife that this sort of devices already existed – they were called long shoehorns. She was so thrilled by the news, she ordered not one, but two long shoehorns (Figure 1). Later, the couple was happy to find that this new device had specific properties which they could use at their own advantage to accomplish another task. They would turn the device upside down and use the curved end to pick up clothes from the floor.

Figure.1 Photograph of long shoehorn

4.2. Approaches to spontaneous inventions

The collected examples during the interviews allowed for the clustering of the inventions into 4 different groups: simple affordances, new methods, new/artisanal devices and the discovery of the assistive potential. The above narrated story about the stroke patient and his wife starts by being included in the 'new/artisanal devices' group and moves on to 'simple affordances'.

When there is lack of information, or lack of suitable assistive devices, patients often create their own devices. These creations are found more often in patients reporting both use of equipment and personal help in their daily tasks, $r = .32$ (one-tailed) $< .01$. One such case is of a patient's husband who decided to create his own 'triangle' above the bed so that his wife could find it easier to get out of bed (Figure 2). He grabbed a rope and cut a piece of a hose through which he inserted the rope. He made a knot above the hose's ends, fixed a hook on the ceiling and tied the rope to it. The patient and her husband did not find the need to buy a triangle since they could build their own. Another patient, this one living alone and having the daily assistance of a neighbour, was promised a hygienic chair by the hospital services. Since it was taking too long for the chair to be delivered (in fact it never came), the patient and the neighbour set out to create their own. They used an old wooden chair, took the seat out and padded it with Styrofoam™ and duct tape. Below the chair, they placed a platform with a bucket on top and their chair was finished (Figures 3 and 4). Not only solutions for assistive devices were found. Exercising devices were also common amongst the spontaneous inventions found. One of such solutions is a mechanism for arm and leg exercising made out of a nylon wheel, rope, steel tube and car security belt pieces. All put together

and mounted on top of a trapeze bar support created an exercise machine to be used by the patient when lying in bed (Figure 5).

Figure.2 Drawing of bed 'triangle'

Figure.3 Photograph of hygienic chair

Figure.4 Drawing of hygienic chair

Figure.5 Arm and leg exercising machine

Another frequent way of solving everyday problems is to come up with new methods using existing objects. One of the mostly used objects in this regard is the kitchen cloth. As an example, there is the case of a patient who lived alone with her husband who suffered from Alzheimer's. As a consequence, there were several tasks which he could not help his wife with. One of those tasks was preparing meals. The problem with meal preparation was that the patient was not able to cut vegetables on her own due to severe hemiplegia. The method she invented to solve her problem only required the use of a kitchen cloth placed on the kitchen counter and forming a nest-like shape. She would then place a potato on top of the cloth, pick up her 'bad' hand and place it on top of the potato so as to hold it steady and, with her functional hand, grab a knife and peel the potato (Figure 6).

Figure.6 Representation of the method to peel potatoes

Existing devices around the house also allow specific affordances for some stroke patients. While for an able-bodied person a long shoehorn has no other evident purpose rather than helping to put shoes on, for a stroke victim it could afford other types of actions. One patient has said: *You know? People having needs, needing this or that, they have to have ideas. They look over at one side, look over at the other and they see that they can only use that thing at hand for the intended purpose. (...) And this is how they take it.* The above introduced couple, who used the long shoehorns, also had another solution to the same problem of picking objects from the floor. While the long shoehorn enabled picking up soft objects like clothes, there were hard objects which were still impossible to reach with it. The solution came under the shape of a long handled dust pan (Figure 7). This couple would use the dust pan as a walking aid to approach the fallen object and then, with the help of one foot, they would push the object into the dust pan. The final step was to lift the dust pan until they could dump the object in a table or any other easily reachable surface.

Figure.7 Photograph of long handled dust pan

The discovery of the assistive potential also deals with existing and surrounding objects. Probably the most illustrative of the collected examples is the one of a patient who found it impossible to wash the pans by herself because she lacked the strength to rub out the pieces of food glued to the pan. Her independence in this task was achieved when she got a set of Teflon[®] coated pans, which would not allow food to get attached to the pans, thus enabling her to wash them on her own. The reason for distinguishing between the group of simple affordances and the discovery of the assistive potential group is that the latter deals with products already in the market, but which have not yet been claimed as assistive devices. These are objects which do not require further design improvement to make their way into the market as assistive devices. These objects are not contemplated in the Government lists of assistive devices, when they are in fact assistive devices for these patients.

5. Implications of the findings for design practice

Design literature regarding assistive devices often states that functionality alone is not enough. Devices must pertain to users' emotions, and to their needs and expectations at both functional and psychosocial levels [32]. Regarding market offer, users should be able to choose amongst different types of the same kind of assistive device in order to make a choice for the device that would better suit their intentions as to what sort of personal

image they would like it to be shown to society and their peers. Up to the moment some possible explanations for manufacturers' lack of interest in assistive device and inclusive products' development have been forwarded. These include the manufacturers' arguments about delivering products to a small market segment, high costs associated with research and development of these products and misconceptions about the appearance of the products [33]. All of these could and have been proved wrong with several examples of market success [33]. Instead of being seen as symbols of disability, or devices which give visibility to disability [15], users could start thinking of assistive devices as a means to express their individuality and identity by taking part in the design process and contributing with something of their own authorship. The finding of the effort and energy patients and caregivers spend on creating their spontaneous inventions could be a clue as to how to fight barriers such as stigma, lack of information and lack of financial resources. All of the identified spontaneous inventions were frequently used by the patients and, in some cases, kept by the owners even if the device was no longer needed, like the presented case of the hygienic chair. Also, a participatory and empathic design approach could provide a means to solve some assistive device use related issues, such as the concern with the expectation of increased loneliness mentioned by people with disabilities as being caused by the use of assistive devices [12]. Hypothetically, the proposed methodology could help in bringing closer patients and their caregivers by the engagement in the design process, thus contributing to the creation of memories which could be positively associated with the assistive devices themselves [34]. This view relates to the concerns mentioned by Hocking (2008) about the need to consider meaning attributed by users to assistive devices and its role in anticipating acceptability or rejection of assistive devices [35].

There are several design cases reporting the benefits of including users in the design process [36]. By involving users, not only could designers benefit from the insights of people who live with daily challenges to their independence, but also patients could feel engaged in the process and react positively to the assistive devices if they felt these could symbolize and remind them of their dedication. Furthermore, users would have a saying in what type of appearance they would like their assistive devices to have, thus bridging the gap between functionality and aesthetics. Designers for their part could benefit from developing empathy with these users and understanding what are their current techniques and methods to solve everyday problems. And, by doing this, designers could learn how to apply this way of thinking to their own methodologies, thus adding to their own capacities and capabilities. For instance, designing assistance in a daily task could be not only about designing a new product, but of designing a new set of actions instead, using existing objects at hand. Or even, the design role could be not about the traditional continuous work flow of getting from concept to final product, but rather to deliver 'gambiaras' to solve an urgent need at a first stage and later to refine the design so that it could be suited for industrial production.

Designers with extensive knowledge on several types of disability could integrate existing rehabilitation teams and visit users at their homes, thus implementing a framework to develop artisanal solutions with and for users according to their needs. This extensive knowledge must comprise know-how in approaching patients and dealing with their emotions, learning how to earn users' trust and trying to take the most out of a conjoint work. This would involve researching and developing a framework for the specific disability being approached and its consequences – both functional and emotional – in regards to the experience users have with assistive devices. Being acquainted with these patients' specific characteristics would not only ameliorate the process of approaching the users, but also help to prevent the negative emotional reactions by using this framework which

would help to link emotional reactions to specific object properties. We have already developed framework such as this for the specific case of stroke patients, whose intention is to predict answers to questions such as ‘How does the finding of the generalized emotion of fear interfere with the object’s appearance and intuitiveness of use?’, ‘How can the object prevent the known feeling of frustration?’, ‘How can the product present a minimal amount of cognitive or functional challenge to the users to enable the feeling of accomplishment?’, and could be later on adapted to other types of disability.

Above all, designers should learn to adopt a posture of apprentices while working with people who live and think about design problems on a daily basis, and they should also have the clear notion of the social importance of their role while developing assistive devices. It appears to us this can only be done by designers trained in rehabilitation issues and who are able to understand and resonate with users’ emotional, psychosocial and functional problems; while at the same time being able to work with and learn from rehabilitation specialists as well.

6. Near future

The pairing of designers and users along with rehabilitation specialists could also allow for the development of low-cost, low-technology assistive devices. Low-technology devices have been said to be useful for the bulk of the population [5]. The above mentioned framework, designed to be used as a starting point for this team work, consists in a network of crossed references about stroke patients retrieved from the literature and our own research and their linkage to several object properties, whose aim is to allow pinpointing the object’s properties to be addressed in regards to each specific emotion it is intended to trigger. The framework is accompanied by a set of guidelines in how to approach stroke patients, and both will be tested by the authors of this paper during the course of workshops with stroke patients and their caregivers in order to design assistive devices using cheap materials and old objects. These workshops are planned to achieve the above mentioned goals, starting by tackling the already known main emotions and feelings of stroke patients regarding assistive device use and task performance: fear, insecurity and lack of confidence. This would be done while developing low-cost assistive devices that could fade out these emotional barriers currently experienced with the devices. Hopefully, these workshops will provide a way for the patients and caregivers to express themselves through design, thus creating new products they would be proud to use in their everyday tasks.

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